

USE OF HOLLOW SILICATE MICROSPHERES IN FIBER
REINFORCED PLASTICS AND SYNTACTIC FOAM CORES

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This paper presents new methods of making fiber-glass reinforced polyester composite for the marine and construction industry. Methods of incorporating hollow microspheres into sprayable formulations are presented. New types of spray guns are described. The sprayable hollow microspheres are used for cores in sandwich type construction, in spray-up laminates and back-up layers for thermoplastic sheet. Results of physical property tests of cored laminates indicate that the benefits gained by the use of hollow microspheres are greater stiffness and reduced weight with reduced labor.

INTRODUCTION

The use of particulate fillers for extending and modifying the properties of polymeric materials has been practiced since the beginning of the plastics industry. A recent addition to the filler family are hollow, low density, sphere-shaped particles. These hollow spheres, consisting of inorganic or organic materials, have particle densities of 0.08 - 0.64 g/cc and particle sizes of 20-200 microns. They reduce raw material costs and lower part density by displacing a large volume and weight of resin relative to their own weight. The use of these hollow spheres has become common practice in many polyester resin casting applications such as

the manufacture of furniture parts and decorative accessories.

The use of hollow spheres as fillers and additives has expanded into many new systems in the last few years. Bowling ball cores are made with hollow spheres so that the weight of the ball can be varied without changing the size of the ball. Cultured marble makers are using hollow spheres for reduced weight and improved crack resistance. Slurried explosives contain hollow spheres for detonation control. The marine and sanitary ware markets are now using hollow spheres for several reinforced plastic applications. Bathroom fixtures produced from gel coated fiberglass reinforced polyester and from thermoformed acrylic sheet backed with fiberglass reinforced polyester are being rigidized by the addition of hollow spheres into the spray-up laminates. Syntactic foam (cellular structures produced by adding hollow spheres to a liquid resin that is thermoset to a solid) cores can be made with hollow spheres by the use of special spray gun equipment. These syntactic cores are used for sandwich type construction of boat decks, hulls, sanitary ware, molds and chemical process equipment. Other applications include easy sanding patch compounds and gel coat backups for reduced blistering, fiber print through and heat line cracking. New uses for hollow spheres are being found at an ever increasing pace.

Q-CEL* - SYNTHETIC INORGANIC MICROSpheres

There are several types of hollow spheres available to the plastics industry. Some are made by expanding naturally occurring raw materials such as volcanic ash. These expanded materials, generally known as perlite, are not uniform in sphere shape, are fairly large in particle size, and contain a large number of permeable voids. Perlite materials are usually lower in price per weight than hollow spheres made from synthetic materials. Hollow spheres made from synthetic materials, which may be inorganic or organic, are usually higher in price per unit weight but their relatively uniform size, unicellular shape, lack of permeable voids and greater displacement per unit weight make them less expensive on a cost/performance basis than perlite type materials.

* Q-CEL is a registered trademark of the Philadelphia Quartz Company.

The newest member of this family of synthetic inorganic hollow spheres is trade named Q-CEL*. Q-CEL is mostly unicellular, microsize, inorganic silicate hollow sphere. Size range is 20-200 microns in diameter and density range is 0.16 to 0.32 g/cc. The appearance of Q-CEL microspheres in bulk is a white, free flowing powder. Bulk density of Q-CEL microspheres is 0.08 - 0.096 g/cc.

The mostly unicellular, spherical shape of Q-CEL microspheres provides it with many applications advantages in various resin systems compared with the expanded particles made from naturally occurring material. These advantages include:

1. Low viscosity at equivalent volume displacement.
2. Low absorption of the resin matrix by the hollow spheres.
3. High compressive strength which gives resin filler composites of high green strength and good strength to weight ratios in the cured matrix.
4. Easy machining and sanding properties due to the nature of Q-CEL microspheres.

An important consideration to the user of synthetic hollow spheres is uniform properties from lot to lot. Since Q-CEL microspheres is a manufactured product the properties are closely controlled to ensure consistency that is not available with naturally occurring products.

COST REDUCTIONS WITH HOLLOW SPHERES

The raw material cost reduction obtained by the use of hollow spheres is determined by multiplying the weight of each component by its price per unit weight. The costs of all the components are added together to obtain the total cost of the batch. Since any given part requires a definite volume of mix, the increased volume of mix provided by a lower density mixture will lead to more parts per unit weight of mixture.

An extra benefit of the increased volume of the mix is obtained in the fiber reinforced plastic (FRP) area. Since the thickness of the laminates greatly influences the stiffness of an FRP at constant glass loading, the Q-CEL microspheres filled resin that yields a greater volume of mix at a given batch weight

will result in parts with greater wall thickness and therefore higher rigidity at equal weight.

SPRAY-UP LAMINATES

Spray-up fiberglass laminates are made by spraying polyester resin from a spray gun that mixes in catalyst (either internally or externally of the gun) and simultaneously chops fiberglass roving to short pieces of 1.25 - 2.5 cm long into the resin spray. The resin and chopped fiberglass mixture is rolled out thoroughly to wet the glass completely and remove air bubbles. The use of hollow spheres as a filler in fiberglass spray-up laminates is a new concept that is used in several applications.

The hollow spheres are mixed with the resin at 0.5 to 8% by weight along with any other fillers used in the system before the resin is used for the spray application. The advantages of using Q-CEL microspheres in spray-up laminates is related to the properties of reduced weight and greater volume and therefore more stiffness at lower cost per volume. Many fiberglass reinforced plastic structures have more than adequate tensile and flexural strength but the laminate must be thick enough to withstand a given force and a given deflection as established by various industry codes.

Table I summarizes the effect of flexural properties of fiberglass reinforced polyester spray-up laminates as a result of adding Q-CEL microspheres to the resin matrix. Also shown is the raw material cost savings due to the addition of hollow spheres at constant laminate thickness. By decreasing the fiberglass content of the laminate and adding 4% Q-CEL microspheres, the weight of the laminate can be decreased 20% and raw material costs reduced by 20%.

Although the absolute flexural strength and flexural modulus both decrease with increasing filler content, savings in raw material costs at equal performance can still be obtained. Laminates that contain hollow spheres can have equivalent stiffness compared to laminates without hollow spheres and with equal glass content, if the thickness of the laminate containing the hollow spheres is increased. The thickness required for equivalent stiffness can be calculated when the flexural modulus of the material is known. The flexural modulus of a laminate is measured by determining the force required to cause

a given amount of deflection of a test specimen. The modulus of elasticity is calculated from the following equation:

$$EB = \frac{Pl^3}{4bd^3e}$$

Where P = load at a given point (e) on the load deflection curve, l = length of support span, b = width of beam, d = depth or thickness of the beam. At constant test conditions of support span, width and deflection, the relationship of beam thickness to flexural modulus becomes $E_B = \frac{P}{d^3}$. Therefore, the thickness required to keep the deflecting load (P) constant with beams of different flexural moduli can be calculated by the equation:

$$d = \sqrt[3]{\frac{P}{\text{Flexural Modulus}}}$$

Table II gives the required thickness of all the FRP laminates of Table I at equal stiffness as calculated by the preceding formula. The thickness of the laminates that contain Q-CEL microspheres needs only to be increased by 480-840 microns to have equal stiffness. The raw material costs of the thicker laminates with Q-CEL microspheres are still lower than that of the thinner laminate without Q-CEL microspheres at equal stiffness.

Although increased thickness is needed to maintain equal stiffness, the use of hollow spheres reduces the amount of resin used as compared to laminates without hollow spheres. The cost savings of using Q-CEL microspheres in FRP laminates of equal stiffness is shown in Table II.

RIGIDIZING THERMOFORMED PARTS

Rigidizing thermoformed thermoplastic parts with glass reinforced polyester has gained wide acceptance within the last few years. Major success has been in sanitary ware such as sinks, vanities, bath tubs, and bath-showers. Gains have also been made in the recreation field with such items as campers, pickup truck tops, snowmobile shrouds, boats, etc. The thermoplastic parts have good resistance to dirt and impact damage and offer a broad range of colors.

However, the dominant element in the success story of the thermoforming is that it is adaptable to production line techniques.

The thermoformed skin can be produced automatically and is followed by the application of the rigidizing system. The rigidizing system is needed because the thermoformed skin is too thin to have the required stiffness and impact properties.

Acrylics have become the most widely used materials for thermoformed skins by offering excellent appearance, processability, outdoor weatherability and resistance to deterioration from detergents and other household cleaning compounds. Polyester bonds adequately to most acrylic sheet. Continuous cast acrylic sheet of 1.9 - 4.8 mm is the leader for use in bathroom fixtures products while extruded sheet has the toughness required for rugged applications like snowmobiles and boats.

Polyester resin reinforced with chopped glass fibers is used widely as the backup material for rigidizing the thin thermoformed skin. However, many new combinations of fillers and fiberglass are being evaluated and used for the rigidizing process. The use of hollow spheres in the fiberglass spray-up system has the same advantages of greater bulking efficiency as previously discussed for regular spray-up FRP. Additional advantages of incorporating hollow spheres in the rigidizing process are: 1) improved adhesion of the spray-up backing to the acrylic sheet; 2) less difference in the thermal coefficient of expansion between the fiberglass reinforced polyester backing and the acrylic facing sheet; 3) savings in material costs due to the bulking efficiency of the hollow spheres, as discussed earlier in the paper; 4) greatly improved impact resistance. A drop dart impact test on 0.25 cm thick acrylic sheet which has been rigidized with fiberglass spray-up using polyester resin is summarized in Table III. The results show the greatly improved impact resistance of rigidized acrylic sheet when Q-CEL microspheres are added to the rigidizing laminate.

SYNTACTIC FOAMS FOR FIBERGLASS LAMINATE CORES

The use of foam core between fiberglass laminates is an established practice when a very high stiffness to weight structure is required. The use of sandwich construction allows more design freedom when compared with the use of solid fiberglass laminates. Rigid

polyurethane foam and end grain balsa wood are commonly used core materials, which work fairly well on large, completely flat structures but are difficult to use on small structures with many compound curves and odd shapes. Syntactic foams made from Q-CEL and polyester resin have the advantages of low core density, high compressive strength, and the capability of application to any shape at various thicknesses. With new spray gun equipment it is possible to apply syntactic foams by spray-up operations on any shape at high production rates.

A recently developed method of syntactic foam application employs a spray gun for the hollow spheres attached to a conventional resin spray gun. The hollow spheres are wetted by resin in the air at the point where the streams converge. Loadings as high as 70% filler - 30% resin by volume can be achieved. Cores as thick as 1.9 cm can be sprayed on a vertical surface without sagging.

One method of spraying the hollow spheres employs a fluidized bed and a venturi powder pump to deliver controlled volumes of hollow spheres. An example of this type of equipment (illustrated in Figures 1 and 2) is the Glas-Mate Dri-Mix Spray-up System manufactured by the Ransburg Corporation. The system consists of a dry particle fluidizing reservoir with two venturi pumps that deliver the hollow spheres to a special Glas-Mate high pressure, airless, polyester resin spray gun.

Another hollow sphere delivery system is illustrated in Figure 3. This system employs a reservoir containing the hollow spheres. The reservoir is under low pressure to force the hollow spheres out through a "T" fitting where the filler is mixed with low pressure air in a delivery line.

Attached to an airless resin spray gun either of these hollow sphere delivery systems can produce uniform syntactic foams. The location and shape of the tube ends for the hollow sphere delivery system must be coordinated with the resin spray (see Figure 4). With the proper configuration of filler and resin sprays, virtually all the hollow spheres can be captured and wetted by the resin. The same filler delivery systems attached to an air atomized resin spray tends to blow the hollow spheres out the resin spray and thus results in waste of filler.

If desired, some fiberglass can be chopped at the same time as the foam is sprayed. A core of higher strength and better impact resistance results.

Sandwich structures with either hand lay-up or spray-up skins have very high stiffness to weight ratios. An "I" beam effect is apparent since the skins provide bending resistance due to their high tensile strength. The further the skins are separated the stiffer the parts.

Experimental cored laminates have been made both by hand and spray-up techniques and have been evaluated with ASTM test methods to determine design parameters for marine and other reinforced plastics applications (see Figure 5). Cores of syntactic foams made from Q-CEL microspheres and polyester resin were compared with common balsa wood cores. Most tests were performed on panels made with the outer skins consisting of one layer of 400 g/m² chopped fiberglass mat and one layer of 800 g/m² woven roving. Koppers 1061-5 polyester resin was used for both the skins and cores. The glass content was held at 40% in the skins. The cores were made by hand troweling syntactic foam made from 20% Q-CEL microspheres by weight in the polyester resin. The common method of construction was to apply the 400 g/m² mat to the mold followed by the 800 g/m² woven roving. The skin was allowed to gel before the syntactic foam core was applied. After the syntactic foam gelled, an 800 g/m² woven roving followed by a 400 g/m² mat was applied. In several tests the complete cored laminate was made without allowing the layers to gel. No significant difference in physical properties was noted.

The sandwich laminates were tested for flexural properties and the data is listed in Table IV. The flexural strength is decreased by increasing the core thickness, but the actual stiffness increases with core thickness. In order to have the required stiffness many fiberglass reinforced plastic parts are made with thicker laminates than required for strength. The sandwich construction method is preferred in these applications since stiffness is increased and sufficient strength is retained. Deflection under load is one measurement of stiffness of a laminate. The sandwich laminates made with Q-CEL microspheres filled syntactic foam cores and balsa wood cores were compared to laminates without cores for deflection under a 90.7 kg load and load required to give a 1.02 mm deflection. A constant 10.2 cm span

was used for all tests with the various panel thicknesses. The panels were 2.54 cm x 15.2 cm. As is shown in Table IV, the resistance to deflection is greater for sandwich construction. Laminates made with syntactic foam cores based on Q-CEL microspheres are significantly stiffer than laminates made with end grain balsa wood cores. The stiffness of sandwich type construction increases dramatically with increased core thickness.

The economics of using cored laminates versus non-cored laminates must be considered on the basis of the physical properties required for the application. When high stiffness and/or lower weight is required, sandwich construction is the obvious choice. Table V shows a direct cost/m² comparison between a standard fiberglass reinforced laminate, a Q-CEL microsphere filled syntactic foam cored laminate and an end grain balsa wood cored laminate, all at equal thickness. The Q-CEL microsphere filled syntactic foam core gave a laminate costing 14% less than does balsa wood cored laminate at equal laminate thickness. From Table IV deflection properties show that the Q-CEL microspheres filled cored laminate requires a 54% higher load than does the balsa wood cored laminate for equal deflection.

A comparison of the stiffness properties of cored and non-cored laminates relative to the raw material cost of such laminates is shown in Figures 6 and 7. For thinner laminates there is no cost advantage for the cored construction. However, as the laminate thickness is increased to achieve greater stiffness, the cost savings with cored construction becomes evident.

Impact tests were run on the cored laminates listed in Table V. A Gardner-SPI impact tester was used for the test. At an impact of 309 cm-kg the laminates with the Q-CEL microspheres filled syntactic foam cores were only dented. The fiberglass face layer was crushed into the core while the core itself was not crushed. The same impact of 309 cm-kg on the balsa wood core caused the fiberglass face layer to crush right through the core to the other fiberglass layer. This indicates that syntactic foam cores provide much higher impact resistance than end grain balsa wood cores.

PATCHING COMPOUNDS AND AUTO PUTTIES

Syntactic foams made with Q-CEL microspheres have found wide acceptance as patching compounds for marine, sanitary ware and auto applications. Patching compounds are required for most FRP applications to fill small holes, joints and other voids produced during the spray or hand lay-up operation. In many application, the patching compound requires a finishing operation such as sanding and planing match the surface which is being patched. Syntactic foams made with Q-CEL microspheres are much easier to finish by sanding and planing than are other patching compounds made with mineral fillers. At the same time syntactic foams made with Q-CEL microspheres give a smooth finish due to the small particle size of Q-CEL microspheres.

SUMMARY

The use of Q-CEL microspheres as a filler in fiberglass reinforced laminates can provide significant raw material cost savings while maintaining strength, reducing weight, increasing stiffness, and improving impact properties. The application technology and equipment needed for combining spray-up operations is rapidly developing and opening new markets for hollow spheres. The use of hollow spheres has moved in the last few years from exotic applications such as research submarines to everyday applications such as furniture parts.

TABLE I
FLEXURAL PROPERTIES AND COSTS OF 3.00 mm FRP SPRAY-UP LAMINATES
CONTAINING Q-CEL* MICROSPHERES

ASTM-D-790 2.5 x 15.2 cm COUPONS

<u>% Q-CEL in Laminate</u>	<u>% Glass in Laminate</u>	<u>Density of Laminate gm/cm³</u>	<u>Flexural Strength MN/M²</u>	<u>Flexural Modulus x 10⁵ GN/M²</u>	<u>Cost \$/kg</u>	<u>Cost of Laminate \$/M³</u>	<u>Cost of Laminate \$/M²</u>
0	30	1.41	113.7	5.38	0.980	1384	4.39
2	30	1.28	102.0	4.69	0.989	1267	4.02
4	30	1.20	91.0	4.21	0.998	1197	3.80
6	30	1.13	82.0	3.79	1.002	1144	3.63
0	20	1.31	77.2	4.00	0.947	1247	3.95
4	20	1.13	60.6	3.30	0.964	1098	3.48
6	20	1.05	50.3	2.89	0.973	1031	3.27
8	20	1.02	46.8	2.62	0.982	1006	3.19

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PRICES IN U.S.A. JANUARY 1975

Resin Cost = \$.40/lb. (\$.88/kg)
Glass Cost = \$.55/lb. (\$1.21/kg)
Q-CEL Cost = \$.60/lb. (\$1.32/kg)

TABLE II
 COST COMPARISONS OF FRP SPRAY-UP LAMINATES AT EQUAL STIFFNESS
 CONTAINING Q-CEL* MICROSPHERES

ASTM-D-790 2.5 x 15.2 cm COUPONS

<u>% Q-CEL in Laminate</u>	<u>% Glass in Laminate</u>	<u>Density of Laminate gm/cm³</u>	<u>Flexural Modulus x 10⁵ GN/m²</u>	<u>Laminate Thickness for equal stiffness mm</u>	<u>Cost of Laminate \$/m²</u>	<u>Kg/m² of Laminate kg</u>	<u>Kg of resin per m² of Laminate (kg)</u>
0	30	1.41	5.38	3.00	4.39	4.23	2.96
2	30	1.28	4.69	3.14	4.22	4.02	2.73
4	30	1.20	4.21	3.26	4.13	3.91	2.58
6	30	1.13	3.79	3.36	4.07	3.80	2.43
0	20	1.31	4.00	3.31	4.36	4.33	3.46
4	20	1.13	3.33	3.52	4.10	3.98	3.02
6	20	1.05	2.89	3.70	4.04	3.88	2.87
8	20	1.02	2.62	3.81	4.07	3.88	2.79

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Resin Cost = \$.40/lb. (\$.88/kg)
 Glass Cost = \$.55/lb. (\$1.21/kg)
 Q-CEL Cost = \$.60/lb. (\$1.32/kg)

TABLE III
IMPACT RESISTANCE OF RIGIDIZED ACRYLIC SHEET

RIGIDIZING LAMINATE ¹ On 2.54 mm Acrylic Sheet	TOTAL THICKNESS		IMPACT RESISTANCE DROP DART ³	
	in.	mm	in. - lbs.	gm - cm
20% Fiberglass + 80% Polyester Resin	.208	5.28	6.8	68
20% Fiberglass + 2% Q-CEL ² Microspheres + 78% Polyester Resin	.225	5.72	9.6	110
20% Fiberglass + 4% Q-CEL ² Microspheres + 76% Polyester Resin	.230	5.84	19.4	220

1. Rigidizing laminate made by spray-up.

2. Q-CEL is a registered trademark of the Philadelphia Quartz Company.

3. Variable weight dart with 0.95 cm diameter nose dropped 132 cm on acrylic side of laminate with 3.81 cm diameter support.

TABLE IV
DEFLECTION PROPERTIES OF CORED SANDWICH PANELS

LAMINATE CONSTRUCTION 40% FIBERGLASS <u>IN SKINS & LAMINATES</u>	LAMINATE THICKNESS mm	LAMINATE DENSITY g/cc	2.5 x 15.2 cm COUPONS ASTM D-790		
			LOAD AT 1.02 mm DEFLECTION kg	DEFLECTION AT 90.7 kg LOAD kg	FLEXURAL STRENGTH MN/m ²
1 Layer 400 g/m ² Mat					
2 Layers 800 g/m ² Woven Roving	4.34	1.52	4.54	-	150
1 Layer 400 g/m ² Mat					
6 Layers Alternating Mat & Roving	5.82	1.54	22.7	4.57	268
8 Layers Alternating Mat & Roving	7.36	1.54	38.6	2.54	237
12 Layers Alternating Mat & Roving	11.05	1.54	122.4	0.813	269
Core Construction	9.09	1.04	45.4	1.90	142
20% Q-CEL* Microspheres					
80% Polyester Resin					
Skins - 1 Layer 400 g/m ² Mat	11.30	0.93	90.7	1.02	112
1 Layer 800 g/m ² Roving	17.65	0.80	154.2	0.64	54.5
Core Construction					
6.35 mm End Grain Balsa Wood	10.97	0.82	59.0	1.52	73.1
Skins - 1 Layer 400 g/m ² Mat					
1 Layer 800 g/m ² Roving					

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TABLE V
 RAW MATERIAL COSTS OF FRP LAMINATES
 OF EQUAL THICKNESS WITH & WITHOUT CORES

<u>LAMINATE</u>	<u>CORE</u>	<u>COST \$/m²</u>
12 layer alternating 400 g/m ² Mat & 800 g/m ² Woven Roving	None	18.94
1 layer 400 g/m ² Mat 1 layer 800 g/m ² Woven Roving in each skin	Q-CEL* Microspheres Filled Syntactic Foam	10.65
1 layer 400 g/m ² Mat 1 layer 800 g/m ² Woven Roving in each skin	End Grain Balsa Wood	12.37

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FIGURE 1
FLUIDIZED BED-VENTURI
POWDER DELIVERY SYSTEM

FIGURE 2
DRI-MIX SPRAY-UP GUN

FIGURE 3
POSITIVE PRESSURE
POWDER DELIVERY SYSTEM

FIGURE 4
DRI-MIX GUN NOZZLE ASSEMBLY

FIGURE 5
SPRAYING SYNTACTIC FOAM CORE
ON FRP SKIN

LAMINATE COST VS. LOAD AT CONSTANT DEFLECTION

LAMINATE COST VS. DEFLECTION AT CONSTANT LOAD

